

Fetal Cystic Hygroma in Pregnancy

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ABSTRACT: Cystic hygroma is a congenital disorder characterized by benign cysts that form due to malformation of the lymphatic system, accounting for about 6% of all benign lesions of infancy or early childhood. This case report presents a 24-year-old G3A1E1 woman with a history of induced abortion and ectopic pregnancy, who was diagnosed with fetal cystic hygroma at 12 weeks and 4 days of gestation. Obstetric ultrasound revealed a single, live, intrauterine fetus with a well-defined thin-walled cystic lesion with multiple internal septations at the level of the occipital region extending up to the thorax, and a nuchal translucency measurement of 9mm. The patient was counseled for medical termination of pregnancy and underwent induced abortion. Cystic hygroma, especially when detected in the first trimester, is often associated with chromosomal abnormalities and poor outcomes. Studies have shown that the overall survival rate for fetal cystic hygroma is 10%, and the prognosis is unclear until the fetus attains 26 weeks of gestation. Early detection of cystic hygroma through prenatal ultrasound allows for timely intervention and informed decision-making. This case highlights the importance of early prenatal screening and diagnosis of fetal anomalies, and the need for a multidisciplinary approach in managing complex obstetric cases. Further genetic counseling and testing may be beneficial for the patient in planning future pregnancies.

KEY WORDS: Cystic hygroma, congenital disorder, ectopic pregnancy

INTRODUCYION

Cystic hygroma is a congenital disorder which is characterized by benign cysts that form due to malformation of the lymphatic system, accounting for about 6% of all benign lesions of infancy or early childhood (generally form towards the end of the first trimester and into the end of second trimester, with the occurrence decreasing by the progression of the pregnancy)[1]. These abnormalities primarily manifest in the fetal neck region and are strongly linked to chromosomal irregularities and various congenital malformation syndromes with studies indicating rates as high as 78%. The estimated incidence of cystic hygroma is approximately 1 in 6000 pregnancies [2]. As cystic hygromas are often associated with different anomalies and syndromes, diagnosing them early during prenatal care is essential. The early identification helps health care providers understand the prognosis plan the appropriate delivery method and establish the best postnatal care for both mother and baby [3]. Hence, detection typically happens during early infancy or through prenatal ultrasound screening. Prenatal diagnosis of Cystic Hygroma using ultrasound is based on the detection of the bilateral; mostly symmetrical cystic formation located in the occipital region. Even cystic hygroma may resolve during pregnancy, this outcome is not linked to the fetal karyotype. On the other hand, if the condition progress to Hydrops fetalis, the prognosis worsens. Research indicated that thickness of cystic hygroma is related to prognosis as well [4].

CASE REPORT

A 24-year-old G3A1E1 with one previous induced abortion under medical assistance and a laparoscopic salpingectomy (for ectopic pregnancy) with 12 weeks and 4 days period of gestation came at the outpatient department with the urine pregnancy test positive done at home. She had additional complaints of vomiting 3-4 episodes and non-productive cough in the last two days. The patient had a history of two pregnancies where the first begin an induced abortion [done under medical supervision] while the second begin an ectopic pregnancy for which right laparoscopic salpingectomy was performed in December 2023 under medical supervision. On general physical examination no pallor, PR-76bpm, BP: 110/80mmHg, CVS: S1S2 heard, RS: Bilateral vesicular breath sound heard. Complete blood picture, thyroid profile are normal, viral serology being negative, blood grouping and typing is O positive. The complete urine examination was performed the results were evaluated as protein and glucose begin negative and ketone bodies were found in the urine. Serology tests, including VDRL (Venereal disease research laboratory), HIV, HBsAg, were normal. On abdominal examination the uterus was 12 weeks.

Obstetric ultrasound revealed single, live, intrauterine fetus corresponding to 12 weeks 0 days of gestation with CRL: 5.2cm and NT being 9mm with an impression of well-defined thin-walled cystic lesion with multiple internal septations at the level of occipital region extending up to thorax with no obvious bony defect – signs of cystic hygroma. The patient was counselled for the medical termination of pregnancy and after taking the consent, she was induced with four doses of MIFEPRISTONE and was shifted to the labor room for spontaneous expulsion and curettage. A female baby of weight 100gms was removed with the placenta weighing 300gms. The external anomalous was noted as Cystic Hygroma

Fig.1: Image showing cystic hygroma in fetus

Fig.2: Ultrasound image showing cystic hygroma

DISCUSSION

This case highlights the importance of early prenatal screening and diagnosis of fetal anomalies. Cystic hygroma, especially when detected in the first trimester, is often associated with chromosomal abnormalities and poor outcomes. The large nuchal translucency measurement (9mm) in this case significant indicator of underlying condition. The decision to terminate to terminate the pregnancy was based on the ultrasound finding and after thorough counseling to the patient. Cystic hygroma, first identified by Redenbacher in 1828[3], is a condition affecting the lymphatic system characterized by presence of one or multiple cysts within the soft tissues. These cysts can range in size from several millimeters to 80mm and usually contain a clear or cloudy fluid that resembles lymph, accounting for about 6% of all benign lesions of infancy [5]. A study of first trimester diagnosis of cystic hygroma; course outcomes, which was studied during the period of 1990 to 1991 the results showed aneuploidy in seven of 22 fetuses [6]. The retrospective study of 57 cases of cystic hygroma detected at 11:00 to 19 weeks of gestation in the routine obstetric population of 24808 women over 12 years. In 2 perinatal diagnostics centers showed the results of 33 cases (57.9%) with aneuploidies (turner syndrome, 42.4% and 8 cases of Down syndrome, 24.2%) and four cases (7.0%) with malformation, whom three with major cardiac defect, and concludes that cystic hygroma is a major ultrasound marker of several fetal pathology and survival of fetus with septate hygroma was very poor (only 6.4%) [7]. the overall survival rate for fetal cystic hygroma is 10%. prognosis is unclear regardless of other influencing factors until the fetus attains 26 weeks gestation; beyond that, there is a 67% chance of eventual survival of those who survived only 42% were assessed to be completely normal at follow up evaluation.[8]. A study conducted on characteristics and outcome of fetal cystic hygroma diagnosed in 1st trimester, the findings that fetal cystic hygroma associated with a poor prognosis and highlights the importance of sonographic assessment of fetal nuchal translucency thickness during the gestational period their

study aimed to determine the outcomes of fetus with cystic hygroma 10-14 weeks of gestation showed the result that 72-fetus had cystic hygroma of which chromosomal abnormalities were presented in 52.7% of cases, that is (38\ 7), including 14 cases, 36.8% of Down syndrome [9].

CONCLUSION

Early detection of cystic hygroma through prenatal ultrasound allowed for timely intervention and informed decision making in this case. The successful medical termination of pregnancy demonstrates the importance of a multidisciplinary approach in managing complex obstetric cases. Further genetic counseling and testing may be beneficial for the patient in planning future pregnancies.

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Cite this Article: Fareha, H., Shruthi, J. (2025). Fetal Cystic Hygroma in Pregnancy. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 8(4), pp. 1682-1684. DOI: https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/V8-i4-14